

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

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Foresight - Digital Forensics

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1. Summary

The rapid and sometimes disruptive developments in information technology complicate the work of international security and specialist authorities as it gets increasingly difficult to keep up with the changes and innovations in IT in the security sector. It is not just a capability gap that has emerged in the security agencies.

A further complication is that a strategic gap has arisen due to the high dynamics and complexity in IT. Unless there is a response to this issue, this gap will continue to grow.

The project CYCLOPES was initiated to reduce this gap. One of the project's tasks is to conduct several workshops in the field of "Digital Forensics". The first workshop with the focus on "Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies" took place in December 2021. This event was used to present in detail many impressions and experiences as well as the current status of European law enforcement agencies. Furthermore, the problems and needs of the participants were recorded in order to carry out a later analysis. The following areas were identified in the workshop for being vulnerable to or affected by capability gaps:

- **Missing functionalities of the currently used software products**
- **Progressive development**
- **Cooperation with Internet Service Providers, Device Manufactures and Software Providers**
- **Country specific differences**

The resulting requirements are examined in more detail on the following pages.

2. Project Cyclopes

The HORIZON 2020 project CYCLOPES (Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners Network) aims to build a stable European network of law enforcement agencies to effectively combat cybercrime. It is a five-year network project with 21 partners from 14 different EU countries. The partners come from EU law enforcement agencies, research institutes, universities and companies. The lead lies with the Polish Platform for Homeland Security (PPHS). The project started in May 2021.

In addition to setting up the network, the core of the project is the joint transfer of knowledge to security authorities and participation in standardization recommendations. In thematically predefined user workshops, gaps and requirements, but also the current status of the authorities for combating cybercrime, are determined. A list of priorities with an increased need for standardization is also created. The workshops are held three times a year on the overarching subject areas:

- Cybercrime – Affecting People Directly
- Cybercrime – Affecting Systems
- Digital Forensics.

The first workshop from the subject area "Digital Forensics" had the focus "Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies" and took place in December 2021 as an online event.

3. Workshop “Digital Forensics” – “Mobile devices and wearables”

Over multiple years mobile phones became increasingly more relevant during investigations. With the invention and distribution of smartphones the amount and diversity of important data available and located on these devices even skyrocketed alongside with their popularity.

This involvement can be on multiple dimensions, as an offender’s, intermediary’s or a victim’s device, but in all these cases being able to analyse the data on such device is crucial, as “Nowadays, mobile devices are part of our daily lives, useful for both work and personal leisure purposes”¹.

Additionally, over the last few years and with an expected growth in population penetration, wearable devices like smartwatches and fitness trackers found their way to our wrists and arms. They collect a whole new category of data, such as health information, or complement other categories such as location data and electronic payments.

Not only do these ubiquitous wearable devices gather and aggregate data about people and environment, we also interact with them somewhat similar to smartphones and use them for more or less important tasks in our daily lives such as online banking, social media interaction and multiple other purposes.

But with this growth in data collection and device usage, companies also focus more and more on data security in order to protect the devices against malicious attackers. This however also leads to increased technical barriers and complications for law enforcement agencies with legal powers to access the stored and processed data.

The CYCLOPES practitioner workshop on “mobile devices and wearables” provided an opportunity and platform to discuss how European Law Enforcement Agencies and partners deal with these technologies today and to identify the current gaps and needs where standardization and innovation is needed. The resulting experiences and requirements are examined in more detail on the next chapter.

4. Result Workshop “Digital Forensics” – “Mobile devices and wearables”

The first workshop was held in December 2021 with 24 participants from 13 European countries. In a short presentation, each participant was able to comment on the following points:

- Technologies and methodologies used presently in Mobile Technologies and Wearable Devices regarding digital forensics.
- Capability gaps and future requirements

What was striking about the presentations was that there was a great deal of agreement among many participants regarding the tools and the methods they used. Many of the commercial mobile phone forensics software products were similar among the participants. It is therefore not surprising that most participants also named the same or similar capability gaps. The following capability gaps could be identified:

¹ Statista (2019)

- Encryption and Passcodes
- Data Extraction and Analysis
- Cloud Services
- Data Storage
- Constantly Evolving and new Technologies
- Relationships with Internet Service Providers
- Relationships with Device Manufactures and Software Providers
- Collaboration with other LEAs and international Partners
- Availability of Forensic Tools
- Awareness and Knowledge
- Legislation and GDPR hindering Investigations

The following conclusions can be drawn from these capability gaps:

- **Missing functionalities of the currently used software products**
Many commercial products do not offer all the required functionalities. In the areas of encryption, data extraction and analysis the EU law enforcement agencies' needs exceed the current functionalities.
- **Progressive development**
The constant further development and fast improvement of smartphones both in terms of hardware and software always pose new challenges for law enforcement agencies. Changes due to fast update cycles, differing hardware and software parts even in one device model and the increasing number of device models creates a volatile area with a need for constant adaption of available solutions and competences.
- **Cooperation with Internet Service Providers, Device Manufactures and Software Providers**
The law enforcement agencies have the big problem that not every international company cooperates during criminal investigations in one country or only up to a minimum. For many criminal investigations, the only way to get some specific information about the communication devices is to get support from the provider or the manufacturer. The problem is that not every company is willing to help.
- **Country specific differences**
Each country has different rules and laws that regulate criminal sanctions, it is difficult to provide a common European guideline or instructions on a detailed level. Even individual agencies in the same country often differ in the amount and quality of available equipment or training and number of staff.

5. Foresight

Mobile devices like smartphones, wearables and tablets are the main carriers of digitization and thus the most important source for the EU law enforcement agencies to obtain information in the respective area of responsibility.

The smartphone, as the most important means of social interaction, has become by far the most important clue and piece of evidence in criminal proceedings. As early as 2009, there

were 125 mobile phone contracts per 100 inhabitants in the EU-27 countries.² In 2017, 65% of EU citizens stated that they prefer to access the internet with their smartphone.³ 85% of all photos taken in the EU in 2017 were taken with a smartphone.⁴ The smartphone is gradually expanding its position as a multifunctional device. In the past, cell phones were only used to make phone calls or to write messages. Recently, the smartphone has increasingly become a personal everyday helper that takes on more and more tasks for the user. It is no longer a problem to use the smartphone to create high-resolution photos and videos, to deal with e-mails, to visit social networks, to make payments or to use the mobile phone as a navigation device.

Also due to the constantly growing number of applications that are being developed for mobile devices, there emerge always new possible uses for these devices. If you consider that in 2021 there were more than 5 million different applications on the two largest download platforms (Google Play Store, Apple App Store)⁵, this rapid development suggests that new applications are constantly being used on the devices and existing ones are being expanded. The resulting new data can in turn be relevant or even crucial for criminal investigations. In order to at least stop this gap between the development of mobile phones and forensic software from widening, the digital forensics tools must also be constantly further developed.

Due to the constantly growing accumulation of data stored in smartphones, the importance of smartphones in criminal proceedings is also increasing. There are almost no criminal proceedings in which smartphones are not evaluated as evidence. In fact, this development is not limited to the smartphone, but applies to all mobile devices. For example, in 2018, global wearables sales were 172 million units, and the forecast for 2023 predicts 302 million units will be sold, an increase of 75%.⁶ Wearables are also of considerable importance for law enforcement because, among other things, they combine health data with geolocation data. In the recent past, some important criminal proceedings have already been evaluated with the help of wearables.⁷

Coupled with the technological development, the security development of communication devices is progressing too; the forensic examination of smartphones and wearables is becoming increasingly complex. Encryption is becoming more and more secure and resistant to attempts to break or bypass it. Encryption takes place not only on the software side but also on the hardware side and makes the extraction and evaluation of the data immensely difficult. In the future, more and more complex and expensive techniques will have to be used by the law enforcement agencies in order to obtain results relevant to the investigation.

Mobile devices will continue to be one of the most important factors in criminal proceedings in the future. That is why European security authorities must now and in the future work together and master future challenges together. A cross-border transfer of knowledge will ensure a steadily increasing quality standard in the individual authorities and ensure that they remain ready for action. The cooperation with universities, research institutes and companies ensure a bundling of knowledge and constantly advancing developments, which enable the law enforcement agencies to keep up with future challenges in the field of mobile devices and wearables. In doing so, both short-term solutions for acute problems of the European security

² EuroStat (2014).

³ EuroStat (2013).

⁴ Cakebread (2017).

⁵ Statista2 (2021)

⁶ Tenzer (2019).

⁷ Lido (2018), Philip Kuhn (2018).

authorities are to be developed, as well as long-term goals are to be worked out in order not to be surprised by future changes.

6. Current development and EU-projects in the area of Mobile Forensics

As already explained in the foresight, the European law enforcement agencies have to face a major challenge in the field of mobile phone forensics. Since these problems are known to the law enforcement agencies for some time, some current EU projects will be briefly presented here:

1. FORMOBILE⁸ (May 2019 – April 2022)
The aim of the project "FORMOBILE - From Mobile Phones to Court" is the development of a European standard for the forensic examination of mobile phones, the expansion of existing forensic tools with new technical analysis capabilities and the implementation of training courses for European law enforcement agencies.
2. EXFILES⁹ (July 2020 – June 2023)
The EU-funded EXFILES project will develop new tools for law enforcement agencies to extract data and related evidence from mobile devices. Led by a consortium of law enforcement agencies, universities and cybersecurity companies, the project will focus on software, hardware and combined methods. It will also consider the ethical and legal aspects of research and exploitation. The findings will be particularly useful for the next generation of forensic experts.
3. LOCARD¹⁰ (May 2019 – July 2022)
LOCARD is a project funded through the European Commission's Horizon 2020 program that would automate the collection of digital evidence in any electronic format and medium. Its goal is to provide a comprehensive management approach to handle digital evidence to be presented in a court of law, alleviating many issues of current art and practice. LOCARD aims to increase trust in the handling and processing of digital evidence and the management of chain of custody by providing transparency and using immutable chain of custody stored with blockchain technology.
4. ROXANNE¹¹ (September 2019 – December 2022)
ROXANNE (Real time network, text, and speaker analytics for combating organized crime) is an EU funded collaborative research and innovation project, aiming to unmask criminal networks and their members as well as to reveal the true identity of perpetrators by combining the capabilities of speech/language technologies and visual analysis with network analysis.

⁸ Formobile (<https://formobile-project.eu>)

⁹ Exfiles (<https://exfiles.eu>)

¹⁰ Locard (<https://locard.eu>)

¹¹ Roxanne (<https://roxanne-euproject.org>)

ROXANNE collaborates with Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs), industry and researchers to develop new tools to speed up investigative processes and support LEA decision-making. The end-product will be an advanced technical platform which uses new tools to uncover and track organized criminal networks, underpinned by a strong legal framework.

The project consortium comprises 25 European organisations from 16 countries while 11 of them are LEAs from 10 different countries.

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